

Supplementary Information:

Coherent Multi-Dimensional Spectroscopy Reveals Homogeneous Lineshape Dynamics in CsPbBr₃ Quantum Dots

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1. Synthesis and characterization of lead halide perovskite quantum dots

1.1 Synthetic Methods

The lead halide perovskite quantum dots (LHP QDs) are synthesized using previously published methods ^{1,2}.

Materials

Lead bromide (PbBr_2 , 99.999%), cesium carbonate (Cs_2CO_3 , 99.9%), hexane ($\geq 99\%$), diisooctylphosphinic acid (DOPA, 90%), oleic acid (OA, 90%) and acetone (ACE, $\geq 99.5\%$) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. n-Octane (min. 99%) and lecithin (>97% from soy) were purchased from Carl Roth. Trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO, min. 90%) was purchased from Strem Chemicals.

CsPbBr₃ QDs synthesis procedures

0.04 M Pb stock solution. The PbBr_2 stock solution (0.04 M) was prepared by dissolving 2 mmol (0.734 g) of lead bromide and 10 mmol (3.866 g) of trioctylphosphine oxide into 10 ml of octane at 120 °C in a 40 ml vial. Once all the PbBr_2 was dissolved (~30 min), the solution was cooled to room temperature and transferred entirely to the big Schott bottle and diluted by 40 ml of HEX. The stock solution was filtered after preparation over a 0.2 μm PTFE filter and stored in air.

0.02 M Cs-DOPA stock solution. The Cs-DOPA stock solution (0.02 M) was prepared by loading 100 mg of Cs_2CO_3 (0.614 mmol Cs) together with 1 ml of DOPA (3.154 mmol) and 2 ml of OCT at 120 °C in a 40 ml vial. Once all the Cs_2CO_3 was dissolved (~20 min), the stock solution was cooled to room temperature and 27 ml of HEX was added. The stock solution was filtered after preparation over a 0.2 μm PTFE filter and stored in air.

0.2 M Cs-DOPA stock solution. The concentrated Cs-DOPA stock solution (0.2 M) was prepared by loading 100 mg of Cs_2CO_3 (0.614 mmol Cs) together with 1 ml of DOPA (3.154 mmol) and 2 ml of OCT at 120 °C in a 40 ml vial. Once all the Cs_2CO_3 was dissolved (~20 min), the stock solution was cooled to room temperature. The stock solution was filtered after preparation over a 0.2 μm PTFE filter and stored in air.

The lecithin stock solution (~0.13 M) was prepared by dissolving 1 gram of lecithin in 20 ml of HEX using an ultrasonic bath (30 min). After preparation, the stock solution was centrifuged, filtered over a 0.2 μm PTFE filter and stored in air.

Synthesis of CsPbBr_3 QDs was performed following the procedure reported elsewhere² with slight modifications.

4.9 nm LHP QDs. The filtered hexane (120 ml) is mixed with PbBr_2 stock solution (8 ml). Under heavy stirring, a 0.02 M Cs-DOPA stock solution was injected (4 ml). After 1 minute of QDs growth, the lecithin solution was added to the crude CsPbBr_3 solution (4 ml). After 1 minute, the solution was concentrated on a rotavapor at room temperature. The QDs were precipitated from the concentrated solution (5 ml) by an excess of acetone (12 ml). The obtained pellet was dissolved in 5 ml of toluene.

5.9 nm LHP QDs. The filtered hexane (48 ml) is mixed with PbBr_2 stock solution (8 ml). Under heavy stirring, a 0.02 M Cs-DOPA stock solution was injected (4 ml). After 10 minutes of QDs growth, the lecithin solution was added to the crude CsPbBr_3 solution (4 ml). After 1 minute, the solution was concentrated on a rotavap at room temperature. The QDs were precipitated from the concentrated solution (5 ml) by an excess of acetone (12 ml). The obtained pellet was dissolved in 5 ml of toluene.

9.4 nm LHP QDs. The filtered hexane (24 ml) is mixed with PbBr_2 stock solution (8 ml). Under heavy stirring, a 0.02 M Cs-DOPA stock solution was injected (4 ml). After 40 minutes of QDs growth, the lecithin solution was added to the crude CsPbBr_3 solution (4 ml). After 1 minute, the QDs were precipitated by an excess of acetone (114 ml). The obtained pellet was dissolved in 5 ml of toluene.

10.8 nm LHP QDs. The filtered hexane (10 ml) is mixed with PbBr_2 stock solution (8 ml). Under heavy stirring, a 0.02M Cs-DOPA stock solution was injected (4). After 60 minutes of QDs growth the lecithin solution was added to the crude CsPbBr_3 solution (4 ml). After 1 minute, the obtained QDs were precipitated by an excess of acetone (66 ml). The obtained pellet was dissolved in 5 ml of toluene.

18.4 nm LHP QDs. Under heavy stirring, a 0.2 M Cs-DOPA stock solution (0.2 ml) was injected into 4ml of PbBr₂ stock solution. After 30 minutes of QDs growth 10 µl of oleic acid and oleylamine were added. Then 2 ml of 0.02M Cs-DOPA stock solution were slowly injected with 2 ml/h rate. After injection was completed, the lecithin solution was added to the crude CsPbBr₃ solution (2 ml). After 1 minute, the obtained QDs were precipitated by an excess of acetone (22 ml). The obtained pellet was dissolved in 5 ml of toluene.

1.2. Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) characterization

TEM images were collected using a JEOL JEM-1400 Plus operated at 120 kV or Hitachi HD-2700. The samples were prepared by placing a drop of diluted QDs solution on coated Cu TEM grids.

Figure S1: STEM image of the (a) 4.9 and (b) 5.9 nm CsPbBr₃ QDs. TEM images of (c) 9.4 nm, (d) 10.8 and (e) 18.4 nm large CsPbBr₃ QDs. (f) Histogram of diameters for 4.9 nm and 9.4 nm P QD.

1.3. Linear Spectroscopy characterization

Optical characterizations were performed at ambient conditions. UV-Vis absorption spectra of colloidal QDs were collected using a Jasco V670 spectrometer in transmission mode. The NC concentrations were determined from the absorption spectra using the absorption coefficient reported by Maes et al.³ For the measurements QDs solutions were diluted down to 20-50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Zwitterion-capped QDs were dispersed in either hexane or toluene.

A Fluorolog iHR 320 Horiba Jobin Yvon spectrofluorometer equipped with a PMT detector was used to acquire steady-state PL spectra. NC solutions were measured in the same dilutions and solvents as the absorption measurements.

Photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY): Absolute PL QYs of solutions were measured with a Hamamatsu C13534 Quantaury-QY Plus UV-NIR absolute PL quantum yield spectrometer. The same solutions that were used to measure PL were also used to measure QY.

Figure S2: Linear absorption spectra (solid lines), photoluminescence spectra (dashed line with shaded area) of 18.4 nm (red), 10.8 nm (orange), 9.4 nm (green), 5.9 nm (blue) and 4.9 nm (violet) QDs. Also shown in bottom panel is laser spectra (grey).

2. Coherent Multi-Dimensional Spectroscopy

The Coherent Multi-Dimensional Spectroscopy (CMDS) instrument was previously described in detail⁴⁻¹⁷. The femtosecond light source was an Ar filled hollow core fiber (HCF) which produced spectrally broadened pulses based upon the 500 nm output from a 120 fs optical parametric amplifier. The coherent pump pulse train was created by acousto-optic modulators. The CMDS experiment was conducted in the pump/probe geometry. **Figure S3** illustrates the CMDS experiment and signals.

Figure S3: Illustration of CMDS experiment, Feynman diagrams for the six response functions.

3. Pulse characterization

Pulses are suitably manipulated to obtain near-transform limited pulses at the sample position. The pulses are characterized using a home built all-reflective dispersion-free transient-grating frequency resolved optical gating (TG-FROG). Pulse durations are determined by fitting a Gaussian pulse shape to the time marginal of the FROG trace. The temporal duration of the pulse is estimated to be close to 10 fs.

Figure S4: a) Typical TG-FROG trace.

4. Sample handling and solvent response.

All the experiments were carried out at room temperature with samples dispersed in toluene. For the 2D experiments, the optical density of the corresponding sample was 0.2 at the band-edge, and the sample was constantly flowed in a 200 μm thick glass cuvette using a peristaltic pump. Pulse energies were ≈ 10 nJ/pulse for all three pulses. Several repetitions of the experiments were carried out on different days. Pure solvent runs were executed to probe the non-resonant response arising from the solvent and glass cuvette windows. The kinetic transients for the X1-X1 and X2-X1 peaks of both solvent and P NC is shown in **fig. S5, a**. The transients plotted in dashed lines are for toluene and solid line shows response of 18.4 nm P NC. The same transients without re-normalization is shown in **Fig. S5,b**, showing that the solvent response is not significant compared the resonant sample response.

Figure S5: a) Kinetic transients from 18.4 nm P NC and toluene for the X1-X1 and X2-X1 peaks, re-normalized to show solvent response. b) Same transients as in panel (a) without renormalization.

5. Handling early time perturbed free induction decay signals

One of the main problems in nonlinear spectroscopy is the presence of early time signals, even at negative population times. These signals arise from Perturbed Free Induction Decay (PFID). We have discussed in detail the PFID signals in CdSe and CsPbBr₃ NC QD. A correction of PFID signals is essential to careful signal analysis at early time¹⁷.

Negative population time artifacts

When time delay t_2 is negative, the order of the pulse interactions is reversed. When $t_2 < 0$ and $|t_2| < t_1$, pulse k_3 arrives between pulse k_1 and k_2 . The DSFD in **fig. S3,b** are reformed into the DSFD in **fig. S6,a**. The rephasing pathways are still rephasing pathways, though the order of the pulse interactions is changed. The non-rephasing pathways become two-quantum pathways.

In the context of two pulse pump-probe transient absorption spectra, the reversed pulse ordering signal is often referred to as perturbed free-induced decay (PFID)¹⁸⁻²⁰, as the pump pulse arrives after the probe and perturbs the free induction decay signal being measured by the probe. **Fig. S6,b** depicts PFID in the context of the three pulse 2DE experiment when $t_1 = 80$ fs and $t_2 = -50$ fs. When the pulse ordering is $[k_1, k_2, k_3]$, pulse k_1 initiates the free induction decay and pulse k_2 then excites the system into a population state (blue). When the pulse ordering is $[k_1, k_3, k_2]$, pulse k_1 initiates the free induction decay and pulse k_3 prematurely interrupts the oscillating electronic coherence so the signal amplitude for $t_1 = 30$ fs is recorded instead of $t_1 = 80$ fs. Pulse k_2 then probes the system and triggers the emission of the third order polarization k_{sig} .

Figure S6: a) DSFD resulting from reversing the order of pulses 2 and 3. b) Perturbed free induction decay (PFID) from reversed pulse order, corresponding to $t_1 = 80$ fs and $t_2 = -50$ fs.

When $t_2 < 0$ and $|t_2| > t_1$, pulse k_3 arrives before pulse k_1 and k_2 . The DSFD in **fig. S3,b** are reformed into the DSFD in **fig. S7,a**. The rephasing signal $-k_1 + k_2 + k_3$ becomes the non-rephasing signal $+k_3 - k_1 + k_2$ and the non-rephasing signal $k_1 - k_2 + k_3$ becomes the two-quantum signal $k_3 + k_1 - k_2$. In the reversed pulse order, there would be a time delay between the emitted third-order polarization k_{sig} and the local oscillator k_3 . This time delay creates spectral fringes at negative $t_2 \ll 0$. As the fringes at negative time delays are significantly narrower than the desired 2DE lineshapes, the fringes can be smoothed by Fourier filtering without significantly distorting the 2DE lineshapes^{21,22}.

After Fourier filtering, negative time signals still appear at -50 fs $< t_2 < 0$. These negative time signals artificially shift the X1-X1 peak to earlier population times, as is apparent in the kinetic transients is **fig. S7 b,c**.

Figure S7: a) Example DSFD when $t_2 > 0$ and $t_2 < 0$. b) 2DE spectrum before Fourier filtering. c) 2DE spectrum after Fourier filtering. Pseudo-TA spectra generating with a 5 meV radius.

6. Modeling of 2D spectra: cumulant expansion and Brownian oscillator

The spectra were modeled using the cumulant expansion to second order for a two-level system, following the work of Mukamel^{23,24}. This method enables the modeling using the transition dipole moment μ_{eg} , the transition energy $\Delta E_{eg} = \hbar\omega_{eg}$ and the lineshape function $g(t)$.

The linear response is:

$$R_{\text{lin}}(t) = |\mu_{eg}|^2 \exp[-i\omega_{eg}t] \exp[-g(t)]$$

The linear spectrum is obtained as the real part of the Fourier transform of $R_{\text{lin}}(t)$.

The third order response is given by the sum of four components, R_1 to R_4 :

$$R^{(3)}(t_1, t_2, t_3) = \sum_{i=1}^4 R_i(t_1, t_2, t_3)$$

$$R_1(t_1, t_2, t_3) = |\mu_{eg}|^4 \exp[-i\omega_{eg}(t_3 + t_1)] F_1(t_1, t_2, t_3)$$

$$R_2(t_1, t_2, t_3) = |\mu_{eg}|^4 \exp[-i\omega_{eg}(t_3 - t_1)] F_2(t_1, t_2, t_3)$$

$$R_3(t_1, t_2, t_3) = |\mu_{eg}|^4 \exp[-i\omega_{eg}(t_3 - t_1)] F_3(t_1, t_2, t_3)$$

$$R_4(t_1, t_2, t_3) = |\mu_{eg}|^4 \exp[-i\omega_{eg}(t_3 + t_1)] F_4(t_1, t_2, t_3)$$

with:

$$F_1(t_1, t_2, t_3) = \exp[-g^*(t_3) - g(t_1) - g^*(t_2) + g^*(t_2 + t_3) + g(t_1 + t_2) - g(t_1 + t_2 + t_3)]$$

$$F_2(t_1, t_2, t_3) = \exp[-g^*(t_3) - g^*(t_1) + g(t_2) - g(t_2 + t_3) - g^*(t_1 + t_2) + g^*(t_1 + t_2 + t_3)]$$

$$F_3(t_1, t_2, t_3) = \exp[-g(t_3) - g^*(t_1) + g^*(t_2) - g^*(t_2 + t_3) - g^*(t_1 + t_2) + g^*(t_1 + t_2 + t_3)]$$

$$F_4(t_1, t_2, t_3) = \exp[-g(t_3) - g(t_1) - g(t_2) + g(t_2 + t_3) + g(t_1 + t_2) - g(t_1 + t_2 + t_3)]$$

The 2D spectrum $S_{2D}(f_1, t_2, f_3)$ is then obtained by Fourier transformation of $R^{(3)}(t_1, t_2, t_3)$ along t_1 and t_3 .

To obtain the lineshape function, we used the multimode Brownian oscillator model, with a static component accounting for size and shape inhomogeneities and a dynamic component due to lattice fluctuations:

$$g(t) = g_S(t) + g_D(t)$$

The static component is:

$$g_S(t) = \frac{\sigma_S^2 t^2}{2}$$

where σ_S is the standard deviation of the transition energies (in units of angular frequency).

The dynamic component is modeled as an overdamped harmonic oscillator^{23,25}:

$$g_D(t) = g_R(t) + i g_I(t)$$

$$g_I(t) = \lambda \tau [1 - \exp(-t/\tau)]$$

$$g_R(t) = \lambda \tau \cot\left(\frac{\hbar}{2\tau k_B T}\right) [\exp(-t/\tau) + t/\tau - 1] + \frac{4\lambda k_B T}{\hbar \tau} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-\nu_n t) + \nu_n t - 1}{\nu_n (\nu_n^2 - \tau^{-2})}$$

$$\nu_n = 2\pi n k_B T / \hbar$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\sigma^2}{2k_B T}$$

where: λ is the reorganization energy, σ is the standard deviation of the fluctuations (expressed as angular frequency), τ is the correlation time and T is the temperature.

Our model therefore has 4 parameters: static broadening σ_S , dynamic broadening σ , correlation time τ and temperature T . The temperature was not varied, leaving 3 free parameters.

7. CMDS spectrum, diagonal and anti-diagonal spectral projection for LHP QD of other diameters

10.8 nm

Figure S8: Experimental CMDS spectrum of 10.8 nm diameter CsPbBr₃ QD at $t_2 = 20$ fs (a). Same at 800 fs (b). The diagonal and anti-diagonal spectra at $t_2 = 20$ fs (c). Same as prior for 800 fs (d).

9.4 nm

Figure S9: Experimental CMDS spectrum of 9.4 nm diameter CsPbBr₃ QD at $t_2 = 20$ fs (a). Same at 800 fs (b). The diagonal and anti-diagonal spectra at $t_2 = 20$ fs (c). Same as prior for 800 fs (d).

5.9 nm

Figure S10: Experimental CMDS spectrum of 5.9 nm diameter CsPbBr₃ QD at $t_2 = 20$ fs (a). Same at 800 fs (b). The diagonal and anti-diagonal spectra at $t_2 = 20$ fs (c). Same as prior for 800 fs (d).

4.9 nm

Figure S11: Experimental CMDS spectrum of 4.9 nm diameter CsPbBr₃ QD at $t_2 = 20$ fs (a). Same at 800 fs (b). The diagonal and anti-diagonal spectra at $t_2 = 20$ fs (c). Same as prior for 800 fs (d).

8. Fitting the diagonal and antidiagonal widths

The model described in the previous section was used to fit the experimental diagonal and antidiagonal linewidths, as shown in Figure 4a of the main text. The optimum is obtained by least-squares curve fitting of the antidiagonal and diagonal widths with 3 parameters described in the previous section: σ_S , τ and σ . The two curves are fitted simultaneously by summing their residuals. The model values were obtained by a method mimicking the analysis of experimental data: for a given set of parameters, the 2D spectrum was simulated as described in the previous section. The cuts along the diagonal and antidiagonal were then extracted, and their FWHM determined.

As the calculations are relatively demanding, the optimization process was accelerated using a surrogate model. The surrogate model $f'(p)$ of parameters p approximates the true function $f(p)$ but is cheap to evaluate. To generate the surrogate, we compute the time-dependent diagonal and antidiagonal widths for a grid of parameters $\{\sigma_S, \sigma, \tau\}$. The surrogate model $f'(p)$ is obtained by radial basis function interpolation on this grid, using a cubic kernel.

In order to ensure correct result, it is necessary that the surrogate provides a good approximation of the true function in the vicinity of the minimum. The best-fit results are therefore obtained by iteratively minimizing the residuals and refining the surrogate until convergence. The process occurs as follows:

1. The surrogate is initialized by calculations on an ensemble of grid points. The initial points are selected to cover a large span around the possible solutions.
2. Fitting is performed by least-squares minimization of Γ_D and Γ_{AD} . The minimization is carried out using the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm, using the surrogate to compute the model values of the widths. This provides a candidate for the optimal parameters.
3. Points are added to the grid in the vicinity of the new candidate, if possible.
4. Steps 2 and 3 are performed iteratively until the optimum converges, and no new grid points can be added.

The calculation grid uses a step size of 1 meV for σ and σ_S and 1 fs for τ . We find the surrogate evaluation problem to be rather forgiving in this case, as the widths vary relatively simply with the parameters in this range, providing a simple optimization surface.

Table S1 : Best-fit parameters. Numbers in parenthesis indicate the uncertainty on the last two digits.

QD size	σ_S (meV)	σ (meV)	τ (fs)
18	13.69 (49)	29.29 (45)	54.5 (72)
10.8	0.1 (12)	32.77 (21)	91.2 (59)
9.4	14.83 (37)	35.20 (45)	42.6 (48)
5.9	15.79 (25)	29.97 (36)	50.5 (58)
4.9	0.00 (-)	35.68 (16)	81.7 (41)

8.1 Experimental D and AD FWHM dynamics along with the model fit for other PQDs

Figure S12: a) Diagonal and anti-diagonal lineshape dynamics of other PQDs fitted with the model.

Table S2: Experimental lineshape width Parameters.

QD Diameter	Γ_{PL} (meV)	Γ_{Abs} (meV)	$\Gamma_{\text{AD}/\sqrt{2}}$ (meV) (early time)	$\Gamma_{\text{AD}/\sqrt{2}}$ (meV) (late time)	$\Gamma_{\text{D}/\sqrt{2}}$ (meV) (late time)
18.4	115	80	24	45	55
10.8	100	85	26	59	58
9.4	77.3	88	22	58	65
5.9	100	112	23	47	60
4.9	115	122	21	63	62

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